
PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE PREDICTIVE MODELS FOR FORECASTING OF AGRICULTURAL PRICES USING REGRESSION AND TIME SERIES**Sandeep S. Ingale^{1,*}, Dr. Nusrat Khan^{2,**}**

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Abstract: Decision making and predictive models play very important any type of business, in which agriculture marketing is also a kind business, where farmers take decision at various stages of the farming like which crop to grow then when to harvest and sell and its store or not so it makes agriculture business more profitable and the mitigation of risk in trade. Hence there is a need for an efficient predictive model that can effectively deal with data analytics with their many predictive models existing, these models need to be analyzed to select the more appropriate and effective model for price prediction.

This paper Analysis of the Regression and Time Series Models for Prediction of Agricultural Prices for potentially forecasting the price values of the agricultural commodities. The forecasted values of various models are compared with the actual market values and select the best fitted model for market intelligence.

Keywords: Decision Making; Predictive Models; Agriculture Marketing; mitigation of risk; data analytics; Predictive Model; Forecasting; Price;

1. Introduction

Agriculture is the dominant sector of the economy. From last decade, the world has been facing wide fluctuations in prices for agricultural commodities. One of the major risks for the farmers, these fluctuations have some regular patterns – seasonal, cyclical and trend -; In addition, there are irregular changes, even sudden spikes. Because of these fluctuations, the farmers cannot take decisions – both in terms of what to grow and when to sell. Description and overview of predictive modeling techniques which are applied to agriculture prices and their applications to agriculture related areas. By considering the importance of agriculture prices researchers describe predictive modeling to forecast agricultural marketing prices.

2. Literature review

Jha and Sinha (2013), in their study entitled “prediction the prices of agricultural products by using artificial neural networks' ' have studied the price of soybeans and rapeseed, based on monthly wholesale prices of these products by using Time Series and neural networks methods. Studies show better results using artificial neural networks for the price of products. In addition, the combination of time series and neural network models shows more accurate results than using one method alone. Ashish and Rashmi (2011), in their study, predicts daily air pollution using wavelet analysis and fuzzy networks. The air pollution is calculated by calculating the amount of carbon monoxide (CO) in the air for 2007 through the Dabshiz wavelet. The results compared with the actual amount represent the effect of addition in the wavelet decomposition model to fuzzy methods for improving the results. In this study, 346 data as training data (95 percent) and 19 data as well as test data (5%) have been selected. Li et al. (2010), in a study have predicted short term price of agricultural products using artificial neural network model. And the results of the study were compared with the results of the ARIMA model. LinearRegression is one of the simplest and most commonly used traditional predictive models. This method is primarily used to predict the value of an output variable given a set of explanatory variables. B. Arputhamary. (2016) proposes a parallel linear Regression and Holt Winter’s models using a MapReduce framework which can efficiently handle very large datasets to forecast the demand, supply and price of the agricultural commodities. Each model gives different values for demand, supply and price projection, the forecasted values of supply and price from each model are compared with the actual market values. T. Miller.(2014) and N. Mishra and S. Silakari.(2012) Predictive models play an important role in decision making. Predictive models will build the abstract model to express the output variable as a function of descriptive variables to predict the future. In general, the predictive models can be categorized into three main techniques such as traditional techniques, data adaptive techniques and model dependent techniques

3. Prediction Methodology

3.1. Prediction and modeling

Forecasting is important in decision making. Using predictive models will build the model to predict the future estimates of the prices of agriculture commodities. In general, the predictive models can be categorized into Fundamental Models using Econometric Models Technical

Models using Traditional Time Series Models, Advanced Technical Models like ARIMA, Neural Network, etc The traditional approaches will estimate the parameters for linear predictors which are used for predictions. Linear Regression models belong to traditional methods.

3.2. Time Series and Its Components

A time series is a sequence of observations ordered in time, $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_t, \dots, X_T$; the interval between times t and $t+1$ being fixed and constant throughout.

The time series collected by the various government and private agencies related to Indian agricultural commodities prices, like Onion, Tur, Maize, Soybean and Tomato prices. They are measured at regular intervals of time, usually monthly or quarterly, over relatively long periods. This allows the disclosure of patterns of behavior over time, to analyze them and place the current estimates into a more meaningful and historical perspective.

Time series can be thought of as combinations of three broad and distinctly different types of behavior, each representing the impact of certain types of real world events on the data. These three components are: systematic calendar-related effects, irregular fluctuations, and trend behavior.

Seasonality (S_t), the trend-cycle (C_t), and the irregularity (I_t), that is

$$O_t = f(S_t, C_t, I_t)$$

3.3. Linear Regression models

This method is primarily used to predict the value of an output variable given a set of explanatory variables. Regression model fits a linear line with the data points in such a way that the difference between the distances of data points from the line is minimized. The linear line of a Regression model is represented by a linear equation.

$$D = I + S * X + e \quad (1)$$

Where,

- D is the output variable or dependent variable
- X is the input variable or independent variable
- I is an Intercept of the line
- S is the slope of the line
- e is the random error
- N is number of observations

If the output variable depends on a single explanatory or independent variable, then the model is called a simple linear Regression model. If the output variable depends on more than one explanatory variable, then the Regression model is called as multiple linear Regression model. In general, linear line of a Regression model can be represented as

$$X_i = I + T_1 * X_{i,1} + M_2 * X_{i,2} + S_3 * X_{i,3} + \dots + N * X_{i,n} + e_i$$

Where,

- X is the output variable or dependent variable
- I is an Intercept of the line
- T is the input variable or independent variable of trend
- M is the input variable or independent variable Moving Average
- S is the input variable or independent variable Seasonality
- e is the random error
- N is number of observations

4. Results and discussion

In this study, to analyze the performances of the predictive models such as simple linear Regression and Multiple Linear Regression, the supply, demand and price variations for the crop Maize has been considered and taken from the year October 2004 to September 2022 (Data Source : Agmarknet) and analyzed. Using the proposed Forecast model, the demand, supply and price values of Maize is forecasted for the year 2022. Comparison of Forecasted values of demand and prices of Maize for the year 2022 with the actual market values of the year 2022 have been done to analyze the performance of the developed models.

The Simple Regression models show large variations in the forecasted values with the market values. In simple regression analysis, the 89% confidence interval with trend and lag price of Maize from past trend in time series also intercept the value of the secondary variable as 0.0002. That is highly significant with the price determination.

The Multiple Regression models explains the 91% confidence interval with her researcher using the following model for analysis.

$$X = I + T_x + M_x + S_x + \dots S_{nx} + e_i$$

The Maize commodity is mainly dependent on the factors such as per Trend, seasonality and previous monthly prices for the commodity in the base year (X_i), (I)Intercept, the Trend (T) and seasonality present with (S). As the Previous month average (Moving Average) Prices is

(M) is dependent on multiple independent variables. This model analyzes that the Maize prices depend on Seasonality, Trends and previous months' prices. Table 1. Comparison of the Actual market price vs. predicted price of models for the crop Maize for the year 2022 using the simple and multiple regression model.

2022	Predicted Prices		
	Actual Market Price(Rs.)	Simple linear Regression	Multiple linear Regression
Jan	1284	1364	1355
Feb	1264	1345	1383
Mar	1786	1330	1587
Apr	1455	1756	1540
May	1510	1487	1597
Jun	1660	1533	1708
Jul	1820	1656	1752
Aug	1744	1787	1791
Sep	1751	1726	1839
Oct	1627	1733	1806
Nov	1538	1633	1734
Dec	1605	1561	1725

Table.1 gives the comparison of the forecasted and real market price (in Rupees per Quintal) for

Fig. 1. Forecasted Prices of the crop Maize for the year 2022

the crop Maize for the year 2022. Fig.1 plots the projections for table1. Fig. 1 clearly shows that the forecasted price values of the simple regression model are in par with the real market values.

5. Conclusion

The price of agricultural products is the key element in agriculture, the conclusion that prices in different times and spaces affect current prices is reached. Through several experiments, analysis of various prediction models made in this work with different agricultural values shows that the simple and multiple Linear forecasting model gives better results for the price compared to Simple Linear Regression and Multiple Linear Regression. The Multiple Linear Regression model gives more accurate forecasted values for demand and supply compared to Simple Linear Regression. This could be offered as a service to the agricultural community providing all relevant information to farmers to alleviate the loss for both customers and farmers and hence improving the overall performance of the agricultural system. The above conclusions are tentative; they need to be reinforced with further study. However, suggest that the detailed econometric and time series analysis with ARIMA and other advanced predictive models is required to predict more accurately.

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